

Viral and Bacterial Pneumonia Classification from X-ray Images Using Deep Convolutional Neural Networks

Ghiffary Rifqialdi^{1*}, Renard Elyon¹ and Amadhea Yudith¹

¹ Bioengineering, School of Life Sciences and Technology, Bandung Institute of Technology, Indonesia

*e-mail: ghiffaryr@students.itb.ac.id

Abstract. *Pneumonia is a disease that can occur in the lungs caused by a viral infection or bacterial infection. In general, the disease can be diagnosed from chest X-ray images by the expert, but due to its appearance in the images, it can be seen as unclear or confused with other diseases. Moreover, the difference between both viral and bacterial pneumonia is hard to distinguish whereas both infections have different treatment from each other. In this study, we used simple CNN, InceptionResNetV2, and DenseNet201 to classify between normal lung, viral pneumonia, and bacterial pneumonia. Simple CNN weights are trained in all layers whereas InceptionResNetV2 and DenseNet201 used transfer learning and fine-tuning for training. The best result is achieved by DenseNet201 architecture with L2 regularization of 0.1. The resulted accuracy and F1 score produced from that model using test set are 93.00 and 93.11, respectively.*

Keywords: deep learning, InceptionResNetV2, DenseNet201, fine-tuning, pneumonia, image classification

Introduction

Pneumonia is a form of acute respiratory infection caused by bacterium and virus that infected healthy lungs causing alveoli swelling [1]. According to World Health Organization, pneumonia killed 920,136 children under 5 years old in 2017, accounting for 16% of all pediatric deaths [2]. Unfortunately, more than 17% of pneumonia babies world death in 2017 is in Indonesia. Early diagnosis is important to prevent deterioration of a patient's condition which leads to death. X-ray images are known as the best method to identify pneumonia, but it is so risky if diagnosed by a clinician. The presenting features of the two types of pneumonia, bacterial and viral pneumonia, are similar and confusing. Diagnosis depends on chest radiology and laboratory tests, especially sputum culture that may take a few days to get the results [1]. This becomes a problem since the images are often unclear and misdiagnose can increase death probability. Miss-classified by the clinician can lead to wrong medication being given to the patients and thereby worsening the condition of the patients [3].

Recently, computers through deep learning showed great success in image classification. Over decades, a computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) system has been used for the detection of lung diseases on chest X-ray images [1]. Developing a CAD system to autonomously diagnosing bacterial and viral pneumonia on chest X-rays is the best option to improve the accuracy and efficiency of diagnosis. Among the deep learning techniques, Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) has shown great promise due to its nice performance in image classification especially in the natural image [4]. This method gives many advantages as they can be easily used with low-cost imaging techniques and there is an abundance of data available for training different machine-learning models.

CNN has been an amazing tool since the convolutional layers within the network alongside filters facilitate in extracting the spatial and temporal options in an image [5]. The layers have weight-sating techniques that help in reducing computation efforts. However, CNN's typically outperform once employed in a larger dataset than a smaller one [6]. This problem can be solved by using transfer learning within CNN if the researcher does not have a large dataset. This removes the necessity of having a large dataset and also reduces the long training period.

CNN as a deep learning field has derived two powerful models such as InceptionResNetV2 and DenseNet201. Both two models can be utilized by doing transfer learning and fine-tuning. InceptionResNetV2 are residual learning that tries to solve vanishing gradient and degradation problem [7]. ResNet is proven to be successfully used in biomedical image classification for transfer learning [8]. Meanwhile, DenseNet, which is a short form of the Dense Convolutional Network, desires a fewer number of parameters than a traditional CNN as it does not learn redundant feature maps. Each layer in DenseNet has direct access to the initial input image and gradients from the loss function. Therefore, the computational cost is significantly reduced, which makes DenseNet a better alternative for image classification [6]. Therefore, this study is reporting a computer-aided diagnosis with CNN-based transfer-learning approach using two different pre-trained network architectures (InceptionResNetV2 and DenseNet201). To do this we utilize fine-tuning and data augmentation methods. Also, we compared the performance on the test data with different metrics.

Materials and Methods

Dataset

Dataset used to train the model is taken from Labeled Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) and Chest X-Ray Images for Classification [9]. The dataset is compromised with a total of 4448 images. There are 1480 normal cases, 1484 bacterial pneumonia cases, and 1484 viral pneumonia cases. Images in the dataset are in JPEG grayscale format. The data split into three sets that are training, validation, and test sets with a split ratio of 70:20:10. The amounts of images that contained inside training, validation, and test sets were 3320, 828, and 300 images, respectively. Figure 1 shows sample bacterial pneumonia, viral pneumonia, and normal lung from the dataset.

Figure 1: Dataset samples. (a) Bacterial pneumonia (b) Viral pneumonia, and (c) Normal.

Data Preprocessing and Augmentation

The data preprocessing is done by resizing and normalizing the images. Images in the dataset are resized from their source size into 224x224. Pixel normalization is done by scaling the image data so its pixel value has a range from 0 to 1.

Deep learning needs an adequate amount of training data to learned and generalize new data. The lack of data availability could undermine the parameter in the models causing underfitting and the learned model to generalize poorly. One way to overcome the problem is by using data augmentation. Data augmentation solves this problem by increasing the diversity of the training sets by applying random transformation [1]. In this study, the data augmentation technique that had been used are rotation, shear, zoom, height shift, width shift, horizontal flip, and vertical flip. Figure 2 shows the images after performing various augmentation techniques.

Figure 2: Image results after performing the augmentation technique.

Model Architecture

Three models had been used in this study. The three models were simple CNN as a baseline model and InceptionResNetV2 and DenseNet201 as pre-trained models that used to perform transfer learning. For simple CNN, the model is split into two parts, which are the feature extraction layer and the classification layer. The feature extraction layer consisted of three 2D convolutional layers with a kernel size of 3 and ReLU (Rectified Linear unit) as activation function, max-pooling layer in between the convolutional layer, and flatten layer in the end. The classification layer consisted of a fully connected layer with hidden neurons of 64 and an output layer that receive tensors from the previous layer and used softmax as the activation function.

DenseNet201 consisted of several dense blocks which in each block contained a layer that connected with every layer in the block where feature maps resulted from each preceding layer are used as inputs for each subsequent layer. Dense block designed so as the feature map size remains the same, therefore feature concatenation can be performed. In between each dense block, there is a transitional layer that consisted of a batch normalization layer, 1x1 convolutional layer, and followed by a 2x2 average pooling layer. The transitional layer performed downsampling of the feature maps [10].

InceptionResnetV2 is a convolutional neural architecture formulated based on the Inception family architectures and the residual connection. Multiple-sized convolutional filters are concatenated by residual connections. These residual connections prevented the vanishing gradient problem and reduced training time [7].

Transfer Learning and Fine-Tuning

Transfer learning is a method that used pre-trained models that had been trained in a particular task and reused it as a starting point on another similar task. This method implementation has advantages of reducing computer resources usage and overcome underfitting issues caused by a low amount of data in the dataset, hence enhancing image classification performance. In this study, transfer learning is performed by using pre-trained models that had been trained using ImageNet dataset that contain approximately 1.2 million images and 1000 class. The pre-trained model is then fine-tuned by freezing the last block of the frozen model base, therefore extracting low-level features of the train data. For the classification segment of the network, a fully connected layer with 512 hidden neurons and L2 regularization were added and followed by an output layer with softmax as the activation function.

Training

The models were trained using Adam as an optimizer and categorical cross-entropy as loss function with a batch size of 32 for training dan 16 for validation data. Callback was used to stop the model training when the validation accuracy is above a certain threshold. All of the models were trained using a learning rate of 0.001.

Performance Metrics for Classification

Model performance was evaluated by evaluating model metrics. The models are tuned to achieve the highest metrics. The metrics used to evaluate the models are precision, recall, F1, and accuracy. Precision is the proportion of positive identifications that actually correct. The recall is the proportion of actual positives that were identified correctly. F1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall.

Meanwhile, accuracy is the fraction of predictions the model got right. In mathematical definition, those metrics shown as below in Table 1.

Table 1: Evaluation metrics equation.

Metrics	Equation
Precision	$\frac{(TP)}{(TP + FP)}$ (1)
Recall	$\frac{(TP)}{(TP + FN)}$ (2)
F1	$2 \times \frac{(Precision \times Recall)}{(Precision + Recall)}$ (3)
Accuracy	$\frac{(TP + FN)}{(TP + TF + FP + FN)}$ (4)

Results and Discussion

Result in Terms of Testing Accuracy and Testing Loss

Proposed models have been trained up to 100 epochs to get the best result (Figure 3). By tuning hyperparameters and using a callback, final testing accuracy and testing loss were obtained in Table 2. It shows that the simple CNN model has higher loss and lower accuracy than pre-trained models. Pre-trained models have a better result because lower layers stores weight from the ImageNet dataset [11]. Therefore, both pre-trained models have similar accuracy. However, the most optimum result was achieved by DenseNet201 models with 22.29 loss and 93.00 accuracies.

Table 1: Final testing accuracy and testing loss.

Architecture	Loss	Accuracy
CNN	34.51	89.67
InceptionResNetV2	29.31	92.33
DenseNet201	22.29	93.00

Figure 3: Training accuracy and loss curve. (a) CNN, (b) InceptionResNetv2, and (c) DenseNet201.

Performance Analysis

The robustness of the used models is further tested by calculating their performance metrics. Confusion matrices were generated from all of the models by evaluating the test set used to validate the metrics score (Figure 4). Confusion matrices helped calculate the numbers of true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives and visualize it, therefore the effectiveness of the models can be determined.

Improving recall usually reduces precision and vice versa. For diagnostics of disease it is more preferred to reduced false negatives than false positives because it can cause the patient's disease to be untreated and increasing its severity, and hence, maximized the recall. However, the consequences of false positives almost as big as false negatives. The patients that are classified as false positives are given a misleading impression that they had the disease and had to endure psychological stress because of the false diagnostics and possibly undergo invasive treatment [12]. The implications of both false negatives and false positives have to be considered. Therefore, a balance of precision and recall should be achieved by calculating the F1-score.

Figure 4: Confusion matrix results. (a) CNN, (b) InceptionResNetv2, and (c) DenseNet201.

From the confusion matrices, it can be seen that DenseNet201 outperformed other models. The lower performance by simple CNN model could be because it has a shallower network than the two other pre-trained models making it more difficult to extract low-level features that are specific for each class, hence the lack of specificity to new data [13].

All the results are tabulated in Table 2. The highest accuracy and F1 score are achieved by DenseNet201. The high test accuracy and F1-score implicated that the model could be used as a supplement for clinical decision-making. Although both accuracy and F1-score achieved for the model are high, the final decision still has to be made by expert radiologists for the validation of the results.

Table 2: Result of evaluation metrics for the proposed models

Architecture	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1
CNN	89.67	90.94	87.00	88.92
InceptionResNet	92.33	92.20	90.67	91.43
DenseNet	93.00	93.90	92.33	93.11

Conclusions

Pneumonia is a form of acute respiratory infection caused by bacterium and virus with a lethal cause that already killed 920,136 children under 5 years old in 2017, accounting for 16% of all pediatric deaths. X-ray images are known as the best method to identify pneumonia, but it is so risky if diagnosed by a clinician because the images are often unclear which can lead to misdiagnosis and increase death probability. To enhance the efficiency of pneumonia early detection, automatic analysis to detect different types of pneumonia from the chest X-ray images immediately after the acquisition is needed. Computer-aided detection with a CNN-based transfer-learning approach using two different pre-trained network architectures (InceptionResNetV2 and DenseNet201) was conducted to classify X-ray images into bacterial and viral pneumonia. The proposed model using DenseNet201 models achieve the satisfying result with 93.00 accuracies and 93.11 F1 score.

References

- [1] X. Gu, L. Pan, H. Liang, and R. Yang, "Classification of bacterial and viral childhood pneumonia using deep learning in chest radiography," *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Multimedia and Image Processing - ICMIP 2018*, 2018.
- [2] WHO, *Global Pneumonia Report 2015: World Health Organization*, 2017.
- [3] M. I. Neuman, E. Y. Lee, S. Bixby et al., "Variability in the interpretation of chest radiographs for the diagnosis of pneumonia in children," *J. Hosp. Med.*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 294-298, 2012.
- [4] A. Krizhevsky, Sutskever I., and G. E. Hinton, "Imagenet classification with deep convolutional neural networks," *Advances in neural information processing systems*, vol. 25, pp. 1097-1105, 2012.
- [5] M. Goyal, R. Goyal, and B. Lall, "Learning Activation Functions: A new paradigm for understanding Neural Networks," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1906.09529*, 2019.
- [6] T. Rahman, M. E. H. Chowdhury, A. Khandakar et al., "Transfer learning with deep convolutional neural network (CNN) for pneumonia detection using chest X-ray," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 10, no. 9, pp 1-17, 2020.
- [7] C. Szegedy, S. Ioffe, V. Vanhoucke, and A. Alemi, "Inception-v4, inception-resnet and the impact of residual connections on learning," *Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 31, no. 1, 2017.
- [8] Y. LeCun, K. Kavukcuoglu, and C. Farabet, "Convolutional networks and applications in vision," *Proceedings of the 2010 IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems*, pp 253-256, 2010.
- [9] D. Kermany, K. Zhang, M. Goldbaum, "Labeled optical coherence tomography (oct) and chest X-ray images for classification," *Mendeley Data*, vol. 2, no. 2, 2018.
- [10] G. Huang, Z. Liu, L. Van Der Maaten, and K. Q. Weinberger, "Densely connected convolutional networks," *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pp 4700-4708, 2017.
- [11] J. Deng, W. Dong, R. Socher et al., "Imagenet: A large-scale hierarchical image database," *2009 IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pp. 248-255, 2009.
- [12] L. D. Maxim, R. Niebo, and M. J. Utell, "Screening tests: a review with examples," *Inhalation toxicology*, vol. 26, no. 13, pp. 811-828, 2014.
- [13] B. Planche and E. Andres, *Hands-On Computer Vision with TensorFlow 2: Leverage deep learning to create powerful image processing apps with TensorFlow 2.0 and Keras*, Packt Publishing Ltd., 2019.